

Benzothiazole Derivatives: Part III. Synthesis and Antiinflammatory Activity of Some 2-(2-Amino-4-thiazolyl)-benzothiazoles

S N SAWHNEY JANVIJAY SINGH and O P BANSAL

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra

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Seventeen 2-[2-amino (or substituted amino)-4-thiazolyl]benzothiazoles have been synthesised by the condensation of three benzothiazolyl bromomethyl ketones with various thioureas (Hantzsch Method) for evaluation as potential antiinflammatory agents. Some of the compounds possess good antiinflammatory activity.

IN a previous paper¹, we described the synthesis of a number of 2-(4-thiazolyl) benzothiazoles as benzothiazole isosteres of 2-(4-thiazolyl) benzimidazole (thiabenzadazole), a well known anthelmintic. The compounds, though inactive as anthelmintics, were found to possess significant antiinflammatory activity in a routine pharmacological screening which prompted us to develop this class of compounds further. This communication reports the synthesis of a series of 2-(2-amino-4-thiazolyl) benzothiazoles (I) and the antiinflammatory activity of a few selected compounds

The synthesis of title compounds was accomplished by condensing the 2-aminobenzenethiol (II, R=H, CH₃ or Cl) with lactic acid to get the corresponding 2-(4-hydroxyethyl) benzothiazole (III), oxidising the alcohol (III) to get 2-benzothiazolyl methyl ketone (IV), brominating the ketone, and treating the bromoketone (V) thus obtained with the appropriate thiourea² (Scheme 1),

Five compounds, nos. 1,2,5,6 and 9 (Table 1), were chosen for preliminary biological testing. LD₅₀ of all these compounds was more than 800 mg/Kg. The antiinflammatory activity was measured in rat carrageen in foot edema test³. Groups of 5 adult rats were used for each dose (100 mg/Kg) of the test compounds which were administered intraperitoneally 1 hr before injecting carrageen in and volume of the foot was measured 3 hr after the injection. The results are given in terms of percentage by which the inflammation in treated animals differed from the controls (Table 1).

I, R=H, CH₃, Cl
R'=H, CH₃, Aryl

1. Δ under N₂; 2. K₂Cr₂O₇-AcOH,
3. Br₂ in AcOH or CHCl₃, 4. R'NHCSNH₂.

TABLE 1—2-[2-AMINO (OR SUBSTITUTED AMINO)-4-THIAZOLYL] BENZOTHAZOLES (I)

No.	R	R'	% Yield	Solvent of crystn.	M.P., °C	Formula	Found		Calcd.		% Inhibition of rat foot edema
							N	S	N	S	
1.	H	H	65	Xylene	247-8	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ S ₂	17.89	27.56	18.02	27.47	60
2.	H	C ₆ H ₅	60	C ₂ H ₅ OH	211	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	13.36	20.32	13.59	20.71	56
3.	H	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	65	C ₂ H ₅ OH	149-50	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ S ₂	12.51	18.22	12.23	18.63	
4.	H	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	67	C ₂ H ₅ OH	178	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ S ₂	11.83	18.42	12.23	18.63	
5.	H	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	60	C ₂ H ₅ OH	198	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ S ₂	12.29	19.01	12.23	18.63	41
6.	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	80	C ₆ H ₆ -PE (60°)	194-5	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	12.68	19.38	13.00	19.81	61
7.	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	75	C ₂ H ₅ OH	178	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	12.86	19.62	13.00	19.81	
8.	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	60	C ₂ H ₅ OH-H ₂ O	169	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS ₂	11.99	18.59	12.39	18.88	
9.	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	85	C ₆ H ₆ -PB (60°)	174-6	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS ₂	12.10	18.44	12.39	18.88	58
10.	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	62	AcOH	245-7	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	15.50	18.30	15.82	18.08	
11.	H	CH ₃	50	C ₂ H ₅ OH-H ₂ O	200	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	16.69	25.70	17.00	25.91	
12.	CH ₃	H	64	C ₆ H ₆	217	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	17.31	25.58	17.00	25.91	
13.	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	62	C ₂ H ₅ OH	204	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	13.25	19.54	13.00	19.81	
14.	Cl	H	60	C ₂ H ₅ OH	242	C ₁₀ H ₆ ClN ₃ S ₂	15.37	24.29	15.70	23.93	
15.	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	60	C ₆ H ₆	218	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ S ₂	11.85	18.60	12.23	18.63	
16.	Cl	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	42	C ₆ H ₆	240	C ₁₆ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ S ₂	10.82	16.72	11.11	16.93	
17.	Cl	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	53	C ₆ H ₆	162	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ ClON ₃ S ₂	10.85	17.01	11.24	17.13	

Phenyl butazone

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Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes using a liquid bath and are uncorrected. Infra red spectra of the compounds were recorded on Beckman IR 20 Spectrophotometer and agreed with the expected absorption bands.

2-Benzothiazolyl methyl ketone was prepared by the method described earlier¹.

6-Chloro-2-(α -hydroxyethyl) benzothiazole (III, R=Cl): 2-Amino-5-chlorobenzenethiol⁴ (31.9 g, 0.2 mole) and dry lactic acid (25 g, 0.28 mole) were heated together at 150° under nitrogen for 3 hr. After cooling, the reacting mixture was triturated with 10% sodium hydroxide solution. The product was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 144°, yield 25 g (60%). (Found : N, 6.73; S, 15.18. Calcd. for C₉H₈ClNOS : N, 6.56; S, 14.99%).

6-Methyl-2-(α -hydroxyethyl) benzothiazole (III, R=CH₃): It was prepared from 2-amino-5-methyl benzenethiol⁴ in a similar manner as described above and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 94°, yield 57.6%. (Found : N, 7.21; S, 16.19. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₁NOS : N, 7.25; S, 16.58%).

6-Chloro-2-benzothiazolyl methyl ketone (IV, R=Cl): To a solution of III (R=Cl) (21.3 g, 0.1 mole) in acetic acid (150 ml) was added with stirring, a solution of potassium dichromate (14.8 g, 0.05 mole) in water (40 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 1 hr., cooled and diluted with water. The product was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 154°, yield 16 g (77%). (Found : N, 6.72; S, 14.82. Calcd. for C₉H₈ClNOS : N, 6.62; S, 15.13%).

6-Methyl-2-benzothiazolyl methyl ketone (IV, R=CH₃): It was prepared by oxidation of III (R=CH₃) in the manner described above and crystallised from pet. ether (60°-80°), m.p. 102°, yield 50.6%. (Found : N, 7.02; S, 16.41. Calcd. for C₁₀H₉NOS : N, 7.33; S, 16.75%).

6-Chloro-2-benzothiazolyl bromomethyl ketone (V, R=Cl): To a boiling solution of 6-chloro-2-benzothiazolyl methyl ketone (10.6 g, 0.05 mole) in glacial acetic acid (100 ml) was added a solution of bromine (8 g, 0.05 mole) in acetic acid (50 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 2 hr and after cooling the solid was filtered off. It was shaken with water, filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from pet. ether (60°-80°), m.p. 102°, yield 9 g (62%). (Found : N, 4.71; S, 11.46. Calcd. for C₉H₈BrClNOS : N, 4.82; S, 11.02%).

6-Methyl-2-benzothiazolyl bromomethyl ketone (V, R=CH₃): Bromine (6.4 g, 0.04 mole) in chloroform (50 ml) was added to a solution of 6-methyl-2-benzothiazolyl methyl ketone (7.65 g, 0.04 mole), in chloroform (50 ml). A solid began to separate when the addition was half over. The mixture was refluxed till most of the solid redissolved (6 hr), cooled and any undissolved material filtered off. After removing chloroform, the residual solid was crystallised from pet. ether (60°-80°), m.p. 108°-110°, yield 6 g (55%). (Found : N, 4.92; S, 11.42. Calcd. for C₁₀H₉BrNOS : N, 5.19; S, 11.85%).

2-[2-Amino (or substituted amino)-4-thiazolyl] benzothiazoles (I).— A solution of 2-benzothiazolyl bromomethyl ketone (0.01 mole) and appropriate thiourea (0.01 mole) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr. The crystalline solid, which separated on cooling, was filtered, washed with a little ethanol and treated with aqueous ammonia. The product was collected, washed with water, dried and crystallised. Yield, physical data and solvents of the compounds prepared are listed in Table-1.

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